

**The Effect of Team Size on Technical Actions and
Psychological Characteristics of Youth Football Players
during Small Sided Games**

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Abstract

Aim: The primary aim of this study was to investigate the effect of team size on the technical and psychological characteristics of youth football players during small-sided games whilst also investigating the impact of game format and maturation. **Methods:** Players from the academies of two Scottish Football Clubs were recruited to compete in bio-banded and mixed maturity SSG. Each week the number of players per team increased: Week 1) 4v4; Week 2) 5v5: and Week 3) 6v6. Whilst the number of players increased, a fixed relative pitch size of 141m² per player was used. A round-robin style tournament was used, which resulted in six Bio-banded and six Mixed maturity games with three different game formats – Maturity Matched (More vs More, Less vs Less), Maturity Mismatched (More vs Less) and Mixed Maturity. The individual technical actions of participants were collected using a foot-mounted inertial measurement unit, whilst the psychological characteristics of participants were assessed using a psychological scoring chart. **Results:** Smaller team sizes elicited a greater array of desirable psychological attributes for more mature players, whilst less mature players' psychological traits remained consistent. Results identified that smaller team sizes led to greater individual technical actions for less mature players, particularly during mismatched and mixed maturity SSG. Results also suggest that game format appeared to have a limited effect on the technical exposure and psychological characteristics of more and less mature players. **Conclusion:** These findings imply that smaller team sizes may be more applicable if practitioners aim to identify or develop the technical and psychological skillsets of more and less mature players.

1. Introduction

1.1 Talent Identification in Youth Football

Football clubs and national associations have invested significant resources to develop comprehensive talent identification (TID) methods to recruit talented youth footballers into their development programmes (Williams et al, 2020). The early recruitment of players into development programmes has been identified as key to long-term player development and providing the club with a potential competitive and financial gain (Unnithan et al, 2012). Elite youth academies have acknowledged that the primary aims of their respective TID methods and development programmes are to produce players capable of competing for the senior team whilst also creating revenue for the club through the sale of academy players (Relvas et al, 2010). With the implications of identifying and developing talented players being critical to the interests of football clubs, the aim of TID methods should be to allow practitioners to make valid and reliable predictions regarding a player's future capabilities (Bergkamp et al, 2019). Commonly, TID involves stakeholders (coaches or scouts) observing a player and then providing a subjective evaluation (Sarmiento et al, 2018). When used in isolation, this method has been shown to lack consistency and lead to the misjudgement of players (Meylan et al, 2010). For example, early-maturing individuals may experience greater success due to their increased stature and physical capability, which coaches or scouts may interpret as superior skill level (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2017). Therefore, objective measures have been devised, which involve a battery of tests designed to assess physical measures such as speed, lower limb power and agility as well as technical skills (Sarmiento et al, 2018; Williams et al, 2020). Elite youth footballers have been shown to possess superior acceleration, power and speed compared to non-elite youth footballers across under-13 to under-17 age groups (Deprez et al, 2015; Gil et al, 2007). The

use of physical fitness assessments within TID protocols allows football clubs to objectively quantify parameters which have been shown to discriminate between elite and non-elite youth footballers whereas parameters such as tactical awareness or game understanding may not be as easily quantifiable. The combination of objective and subjective TID methods through a physical testing battery followed by match-play, either full-sized or SSG, is commonly observed in youth football (le Gall et al, 2010). The difficulty with implementing TID protocols during adolescence is that the process can be confounded due to the impact of growth and maturation (Meylan et al, 2010; Towlson et al, 2018).

1.2 Growth and Maturation in Youth Football

Adolescents experience an accelerated period of growth which typically onsets between 9 and 11 years of age and concludes between 13 and 15 years, known as peak height velocity (PHV) (Towlson et al, 2021a; Towlson et al, 2018). The timing of anthropometric development is asynchronous with age and is highly individualised in nature which can lead to considerable variation in anthropometric characteristics (i.e., stature and mass) and influential physical fitness traits (i.e., speed and power) when players are grouped based on chronological age (CA) (Deprez et al, 2015; Lovell et al, 2015; Towlson et al, 2019). CA-matched groups allow for competition where players possess similar cognitive, motor, and social skills and playing experience (Cumming et al, 2018a). However, the inter-individual differences in maturation present during adolescence (Malina et al, 2015) may hinder the identification of talented players within this format (Meylan et al, 2010). For example, early-maturing individuals may experience greater success due to their increased stature and physical capability, which coaches or scouts may interpret as superior skill level (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2017). Research has identified a maturity-related selection bias

within youth football (Lovell et al, 2015; Towlson et al, 2022); therefore, stakeholders must consider the impact of growth and maturation during TID. A symptom of this selection bias is an under-selection and under-representation of late-maturing individuals within football academies despite, in some cases, late-maturing players possessing greater technical and psychological skill sets (Zuber et al, 2016). Talent selectors have acknowledged that the technical and psychological characteristics of youth football players are desirable during the TID process (Sarmiento et al, 2018). Therefore, practices that allow for the identification of those desirable attributes should be considered during TID processes (Unnithan et al, 2012). Once a player has been identified and recruited into the development programme of a club, consideration must be given to the environment that facilitates the further development of players' skill sets to allow them to reach their full potential (Sarmiento et al, 2018). Factors such as specific coach support and appropriate training stimulus are essential when creating a suitable learning environment (Sarmiento et al, 2018; Williams et al, 2020), particularly in youth football where maturation can impact talent development.

1.3 Growth and Maturation and Technical Development in Youth Football

The competitive nature of academy football may encourage early-maturing individuals to adopt a playing style that relies heavily on their physical strengths to the detriment of the development of technical and tactical skills (Malina et al, 2015). During adolescence, there is a period of heightened neural plasticity allowing the strengthening of frequently used neural connections and, conversely, the removal of rarely used neural connections (Blakemore et al, 2010). Therefore, neglecting technical and tactical skills during early adolescence can have significant long-term consequences regarding skill development (Cumming et al, 2018a). Furthermore, early-maturing players may be ill-prepared technically and tactically to

make the transition to senior football where the maturity-related anthropometric and physical fitness differences are attenuated (Malina et al, 2015). Developing players who don't possess the required skillsets to cope with the transition to senior football would be a failure on behalf of the academy, with academy practitioners acknowledging that ensuring players are prepared for the demands of senior football is a primary aim of youth football academies (Relvas et al, 2017). In contrast, late-maturing individuals must develop and exhibit enhanced technical skills to ensure they remain competitive in academy football – this is referred to as the underdog hypothesis (Cumming et al, 2018b). For the benefits of the underdog hypothesis to be realised, it is imperative that late-maturing individuals are selected and then retained within the academy environment (Cumming et al, 2018b). The difficulty for talent selectors is that the technical and tactical skills of late-maturing players may be masked due to the physical superiority of an early-maturing player inhibiting the emergence of such skills (Reeves et al, 2019). Therefore, creating an environment whereby the early maturing individuals' technical and tactical skills are challenged appropriately, and late maturing players can express their skill sets is critical to the development and (de)selection of both groups.

1.4 Growth and Maturation and Psychological Development in Youth Football

The greater challenge experienced by late-maturing players is thought to facilitate the development of superior psychological skills (Cumming et al, 2018b). Zuber et al (2016) conducted a three-year longitudinal study among a cohort of elite Swiss youth football players to provide a holistic examination of the development of youth footballers. Players were assessed on constructs surrounding psychological, technical, and biological maturity characteristics and it was identified that late-maturing players exhibit more adaptive

psychological characteristics and greater technical competency (Zuber et al, 2016). It is important to acknowledge that the method used to assess the biological maturity of participants was the Mirwald equation (Mirwald et al, 2002), which has received criticism surrounding its validity and reliability (Malina & Koziel, 2014). Youth soccer players, ranging from 11 to 16 years of age, were asked to complete focus group interviews and questionnaires to ascertain their experiences of competing in bio-banding (BB) competition as well as self-regulated learning capabilities (Cumming et al, 2018a; Cumming et al, 2018b). Results demonstrated that late-maturing youth football players engaged more in behaviours such as self-evaluation or self-reflection. The more adaptive skill sets shown by late-maturing players have been suggested to mitigate physical disadvantages caused by delayed maturation, however, there is no evidence to suggest these skills are developed because of the more significant challenge posed or whether late-maturing players are required to possess these qualities or face de-selection from academies (Cumming et al, 2018a; Cumming et al, 2018b). Despite late-maturing players displaying more adaptive psychological skill sets, they failed to transition to national and regional talent squads with early-maturing players being allocated the positions (Zuber et al, 2016). Regarding the early-maturing players selected and retained within academy structures, practitioners must consider how this cohort will develop the required psychological skillsets. Early-maturing players aren't exposed to the same developmental challenges, such as having to problem-solve and be resilient enough to overcome the challenge of competing against the physically superior competition (Towson & Cumming, 2022). Once players transition into senior football, the temporary maturity-related advantages experienced by early maturing players are removed and as a result, they may be ill-prepared to cope with the demands of senior football (Cumming et al, 2018a; Malina et al, 2015). Preparing players for the transition to

senior football is one of the ultimate aims of football academies (Relvas et al, 2017).

Therefore, it is the responsibility of the academies to provide players with an environment that appropriately prepares them for the demands of senior football. Practitioners must then consider how early-maturing players are exposed to challenging learning environments that facilitate the development of desirable technical and psychological skill sets.

Furthermore, creating an environment whereby the expression of late-maturing players' technical and psychological skills isn't masked by their physically superior early-maturing counterparts is vital for TID and talent development.

1.5 Bio-Banding and Youth Football

To account for the significant variations in maturation present within CA groups, BB is a proposed method in which players are grouped based on their biological age in place of CA (Cumming et al, 2017). Thus, reducing, but not eliminating, the maturity-associated differences in anthropometric and key physical fitness traits that can be present between players during CA competition (Abbot et al, 2021; Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2018a; Cumming et al, 2017). Within academy football environments, BB is considered an attractive method for reducing the over-selection of early-maturing players due to their superior size and athleticism as a result of advanced maturation (Deprez et al, 2015; Lovell et al, 2015). The concept of BB has also been adopted on a national scale with football federations such as the Belgian FA implementing initiatives such as the 'Futures Squad' program. The Belgian FA Futures youth teams span across the U15 to U17 age groups and were created in an attempt to combat the problems associated with growth and maturation during adolescence. Late-maturing players are afforded the opportunity to represent their country and gain access to the quality training offered by the Belgian FA. Future squad tournaments

have become prominent within European football, with federations such as Belgian, Swedish, Danish and Polish FA competing in four-team tournaments, emphasizing the growing popularity of BB initiatives at a federation level within football. In 2012, the Elite Player Performance Plan (EPPP) was launched by the English Premier League in conjunction with the English Football League and the English Football Association. The EPPP aims to increase the volume and quality of home-grown players long-term. As part of the EPPP, a BB programme was implemented where a series of multi-team tournaments are organised each season in an attempt to combat the issues surrounding growth and maturity within youth football (Premier League, 2019). The inclusion of BB initiatives within a long-term programme aimed at finding innovative and effective ways of increasing the number and quality of home-grown players emphasises the increasing popularity of BB as a method of enhancing the development of youth football players at both a club and national scale.

Currently, research suggests that BB can expose players to unique challenges and learning opportunities (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2018a) through diversified game constraints and task demands (Abbot et al, 2019; Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al 2018a; Lovell et al, 2021). Qualitative research conducted by Cumming et al (2018a) and Bradley et al (2019) investigated the experiences of players post-BB match play. Participants were recruited from U10 to U15 academy squads of professional football clubs and competed in various BB matches with team sizes ranging from 6v6 SSG to the traditional 11v11 format. Upon completion of the games, the player's experiences were gathered using questionnaires and focus group interviews. Generally, the concept of BB was well received by both early and late maturing players, with both groups describing it as a positive experience that offered a different challenge compared to CA competition (Bradley et al,

2019; Cumming et al, 2018a). Early-maturing players indicated that BB posed an increased physical challenge which in turn emphasised the use of their technical and tactical skills whilst also encouraging new ways to process information and develop decision-making (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2018a). In contrast, late-maturing players described a reduced physical challenge during BB compared to CA competition allowing greater expression of their technical, physical, and psychological skillsets (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2018a). BB was also reported to allow late-maturing players to greater impact the game whilst adopting leadership positions (Bradley et al, 2019; Cumming et al, 2018a). A consequence of the unconscious selection bias towards early-maturing players is that late-maturing players are likely deselected from talent development programmes and therefore denied access to high-quality coaching and training resources as well as greater competition levels (Malina et al, 2015). The reduced physical challenge associated with BB for less mature players allows them to express their skillsets which in turn may allow TID practitioners to better identify desirable attributes among said cohort and ultimately lead to the retention of less mature players within talent development programmes.

Whilst the applied research into the efficacy of BB is limited, the current body of research has focused on investigating the effect of BB on various aspects of performance such as physical prowess, technical attributes, tactical understanding, and psychological characteristics. Research is predominantly conducted during traditional match-play (11v11 or 9v9) between players from multiple academies (Abbot et al, 2019; Romann et al, 2020; Lüdin et al, 2021) or during SSG - typically 4v4 (Towlson et al, 2021a; Towlson et al, 2021b; Towlson et al 2021c). During match-play, BB has been shown to manipulate the technical demand placed upon both early and late-maturing players compared to CA games with

greater emphasis placed on an individual's technical skills (Abbot et al, 2019; Romann et al, 2020; Lüdin et al, 2021). The difficulty with implementing BB within traditional match-play formats is that academy squads may not possess the required number of players to conduct such matches. For example, the over-representation of early-maturing players may impact the use of BB concerning late-maturing players as there may not be a sufficient number of late-maturing players within the academy to conduct BB using traditional match-play formats. Therefore, cross-academy BB match-play may be necessary, which could prove problematic logistically. SSG may be a more applicable method for applying BB within an academy, as squads should contain sufficient numbers to divide players into maturity-matched teams for SSG. Historically, SSG have been used to improve players' physical condition whilst offering the opportunity to develop technical and tactical skills concurrently (Hill-Hass et al, 2009). However, the design of the SSG is critical to ensure its effectiveness in achieving the desired outcome (Hill-Hass et al, 2009). Game constraints such as pitch dimensions (Martone et al, 2017; Olthof et al, 2018) and team size (the number of players per team) (Da Silva et al, 2011; Hill-Hass et al, 2009) have been shown to influence the physical, technical, and tactical demands of traditional SSG. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the effect of game constraints on BB SSG to ensure its efficacy. For example, suppose the desired outcome of BB is to develop the technical skills of an early maturing player. In that case, practitioners must understand which game constraint is most effective in promoting the desired outcome. During traditional match-play, BB has been shown to manipulate the frequency of certain technical actions compared to CA competition (Abbot et al, 2019; Romann et al, 2020; Lüdin et al, 2021). Early-maturing players were found to display a greater number of short passes but fewer dribbles during BB compared to CA competition, with researchers speculating that the increased physical challenge of BB

reduced the ease at which early-maturing players could dribble past opponents and, therefore, were required to complete more short passes to advance towards goal (Abbot et al, 2019). The reduced physical challenges experienced by late-maturing players during BB promoted greater tackling behaviours and conquered balls compared to CA competition (Abbot et al, 2019; Lüdin et al, 2021) with an increased tendency to engage in dribbles and attacking actions towards the opponent's goal (Lüdin et al, 2021). However, BB SSG was found to have limited effect on players' physical, technical, and tactical characteristics (Towlson et al, 2021b; Towlson et al, 2021c). The use of maturity-mismatched BB was however found to elicit an increase in several desirable psychological traits among pre-PHV players (Towlson et al, 2021a). Towlson et al (2021a) investigated the effect of different relative pitch sizes during 4v4 maturity matched, mismatched, and mixed maturity SSG and found that smaller relative pitch areas resulted in an increased number of tactical behaviours and technical actions. This suggests that relative pitch size is a game constraint that can influence the expression of the technical and tactical behaviours during BB SSG. Currently, to our knowledge, no research examines the effect that team size has on the display of desirable performance characteristics of youth football players during BB SSG, despite research identifying team size as a game constraint that influences performance during traditional SSG (Da Silva et al, 2011; Hill-Hass et al, 2009). Therefore, the primary aim of this study is to investigate the effect of team size (game constraint), when relative pitch size is controlled for, on the technical and psychological performance of youth academy football players during BB (maturity matched and mismatched) and mixed-maturity SSG. In addition, the effect of game format and maturation on the technical and psychological characteristics was also within the scope of this study.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Fifty-three players from the youth academies of two professional Scottish football clubs (age 13.4 ± 0.9 years, stature 161.4 ± 10.8 cm and body mass 49.5 ± 10 kg) were recruited for this study. Initially, only 48 players were due to complete the study; however, in the third week of testing, five players withdrew from the study due to injury and were replaced with players of a similar maturity status to ensure that the efficacy of the study was maintained. Despite being replaced in the third week of testing, the injured player's data was still included in the study for the first two weeks, and the replacement players provided the data for the third week, hence the 53 players. Before the commencement of the study, institutional ethics committee approval was obtained, as well as informed, written consent from both the participants and their parents/guardians.

2.2 Maturity Assessment

Academy sports scientists employed by each club collected the required anthropometric data - stature, seated stature, and mass - as part of routine assessment within the academy and shared the data with the lead researcher for the present study. Maturity status was estimated using the Fransen method (Fransen et al, 2018). Age at peak height velocity (APHV) and maturity offset (MO) were then derived from the maturity ratio. It is acknowledged that obtaining maturity status via the assessment of secondary sex characteristics or skeletal maturation via X-ray is deemed the 'gold standard' (Unnithan et al, 2012), however, their use within a youth population is difficult due to the invasive nature and requirement for trained staff and expensive equipment (Malina et al, 2015). Therefore, it is accepted that non-invasive measures of maturation may be more applicable to the applied setting. The Khamis-Roche method (Khamis & Roche, 1994) is the favoured non-

invasive method for assessing maturity status within youth football (Salter et al, 2020). It has been validated within Portuguese youth football players against substantiated markers of maturity such as skeletal age (Malina et al, 2012). However, there were practical limitations that impacted its use within the current study. The requirement for parental height proved problematic as there was the potential that, in some instances, players may not be able to provide said data. Therefore, it was decided that the Fransen method was the most appropriate non-invasive assessment due to its use in field-based research involving similar cohorts to the present study (Lovell et al, 2019; Gil et al, 2014). Previous MO methods (Mirwald et al, 2002; Moore et al, 2015) have adopted a linear approach to estimate the non-linear process of biological maturation (Rogal et al, 2000). The new strategy adopted by Fransen et al (2018) aims to reduce the prediction error by fitting a non-linear relationship between meaningful anthropometric predictors of maturity and using a maturity ratio in place of a maturity offset. The process of somatic growth is non-linear; therefore, it is hypothesised using a non-linear relationship in place of the traditional linear relationship will improve the accuracy of the prediction (Fransen et al, 2018). Using a maturity ratio in place of a MO allows for a superior model fit, regardless of a significant difference in APHV and chronological age (Fransen et al, 2018). The Fransen method was validated within a sample of youth football players, similar to the cohort used in the present study (Fransen et al, 2018). A commonly cited problem with MO is that the prediction error increases for individuals who are further away from their APHV (Kozziel & Malina, 2018), and whilst the Fransen method (Fransen et al, 2018) aims to reduce said prediction error, it was essential to recognise. Previous research conducted in youth football has excluded players who are ± 2 years from APHV to account for this (McMaster et al, 2021). A similar approach

was conducted in this study; however, an exclusion threshold of ± 2.6 years from APHV was used to ensure a sufficient number of players to complete the study.

2.3 Experimental Design

Participants were ranked based on their MO and split at the median (-1.1 years) to create a biologically more mature group (-1.0 to +1.2 years) and a biologically less mature group (-1.1 to -2.6 years). Both groups were significantly different from each other in age, stature, mass, and MO ($p < 0.001$). A similar approach was adopted by Lüdin et al (2021) and Romann et al (2020) in previous research, where they investigated the effect of BB on crucial performance characteristics in youth football, with participants hailing from the U13 and U14 academy squads of professional football clubs. This present study randomly assigned participants to one of four teams for BB competition – More Mature A or B and Less Mature A or B. Mixed maturity teams consisting of more and less mature players were also created. Players were randomly assigned to either mixed maturity A, B, C or D with teams comprising of an even amount of more and less mature players except for 5v5 where Mixed Maturity A and B consisted of three more mature and two less mature players while Mixed Maturity C and D teams consisted of two more mature and three less mature players. Mixed maturity teams aimed to reflect the current composition of academy teams within youth football and acted as a surrogate control group. BB and Mixed games were completed in a round-robin style tournament resulting in six BB and six Mixed matches, which created three game types – Maturity Matched (More vs More, Less vs Less), Maturity Mismatched (More vs Less) and Mixed Maturity (see appendix 1). This format was conducted at each academy one evening per week for three consecutive weeks, resulting in 72 SSG being played. Each week the number of players per team increased: Week 1) 4v4; Week 2) 5v5; and Week 3) 6v6. Whilst

the number of players increased, a fixed relative pitch size of 141m^2 per player was used. This specific relative pitch size was derived from the current minimum Scottish Football Association guidelines regarding the pitch dimensions for a 7-a-side match (55m x 36m). For example, the pitch area for 7v7 is (55 x 36) 1980m^2 , so the area per player is ($1980 \div 14$) 141m^2 . Therefore, 4v4 pitch size was obtained using the following method: The required pitch area is (141×8) 1128m^2 , so dimensions are 40.3m x 28m ($40.3 \times 28 = 1128.4$), resulting in an area per player of 141.05m^2 ($1128.4 \div 8$). The same method was used to obtain the pitch dimensions of 5v5 (44.1m x 32m) and 6v6 (47m x 36m). Like previous research (Towlson et al, 2021a; Towlson et al, 2021b; Towlson et al, 2021c), each SSG game was five minutes in duration. At any one time, only two teams were competing in an SSG whilst the other two teams were playing football tennis to ensure the activity of players not competing was standardised throughout the study. There was a five-minute washout period between the BB and mixed maturity matches. Each SSG was conducted on a 3-G synthetic surface with two mini goals (2m x 1m) placed at the mid-point of each end on the field. No goalkeepers were allowed in this present study, and players were restricted from scoring until they were in the opposing team's half. A multi-ball system was used to keep the game flowing, with footballs placed outside the perimeter of the pitch. Unless communicating a refereeing decision or the score line, coaches and researchers were restricted from interacting with players to control for the effects of verbal feedback or encouragement.

2.4 Data Collection

Data collection was conducted during the competitive academy season, with players following a regular weekly schedule consisting of two to three training sessions and one competitive match. Each data collection session was conducted at the same venue and on

the same evening as regularly scheduled training (Club 1 – Monday, Club 2 – Thursday) to ensure the participants' regular weekly activities were controlled for. Technical data was collected via foot-mounted inertial measuring units (IMU) (PlayerMaker™, Tel Aviv, Israel). Each IMU included a 16 g triaxial accelerometer and a $2000^{\circ}\cdot\text{sec}^{-1}$ triaxial gyroscope, which were incorporated from the MPU-9150 multi-chip motion tracking module (InvenSense, California, USA). On the player's arrival, an IMU was fitted on each boot, placed within tightly held silicone straps supplied by the manufacturer. The IMUs were placed over the player's boots on the lateral malleoli. Players were given the same IMU for each testing session to control for inter-unit reliability issues. A study conducted by Marris et al (2022) compared the inter-unit reliability and validity of the IMUs compared to retrospective video analysis. Results showed good inter-unit reliability (Proportion of agreement (PA) = 95.9% - 96.9%, Coefficient of Variance (CV) = 1.4% - 2.9%) and validity (PA = 95.1% - 100.0%). The study conducted by Marris et al (2022) investigated the reliability of foot-mounted IMU within controlled technical tasks, which they recognised weren't reflective of competitive match-play. For example, technical actions may be performed during football using alternate body parts, the head or thigh, which the foot-mounted IMU cannot detect. Therefore, it is important to recognise the volume of technical actions may be underreported (Marris et al, 2022). Each device was activated via a Bluetooth connection to an iPad (Apple Inc, California) before the session and data were uploaded to the manufacturer's cloud-based software (v.3.22.0.02) immediately post-session using the iPad. Each SSG's start and end times were recorded and then tagged before exporting the data into Microsoft Excel 2020 from manufacturers' cloud-based software. The technical metrics selected for analysis revolved around the participant's involvement with the ball and are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptions of the Technical Performance Metrics Collected

<i>Technical Metric</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Touches</i>	The total number of touches a player had.
<i>Releases</i>	The total number of releases actions a player had (pass or kick)
<i>Time on the Ball</i>	The total time a player had possession of the ball.
<i>Ball Possessions*</i>	The total number of ball possessions a player had.

*Ball Possession is defined as a release action **or**, a sequence of 3 touches **or**, a player covering at least six metres with the ball

Psychological data was collected using a psychological-scoring chart (see Appendix 2), previously used by Towlson et al (2021b). The chart consisted of four categories (Confidence, Competitiveness, X-factor and Positive Attitude), each representing a critical psychological characteristic for youth coaches and talent selectors when recruiting a player for talent identification programmes (Larkin and O’Connor 2017; Towlson et al. 2019). Multiple coaches from each participating club were provided with the scoring chart before the commencement of the testing session and assigned a team(s) they were responsible for scoring. Coaches were provided with a period to familiarise themselves with the scoring chart and offered the opportunity to ask any questions they felt were relevant before the testing sessions. Each scoring chart defined the specific psychological characteristics being assessed to provide the coaches with an understanding of what they were assessing. Assessors scored each desirable trait between 1 and 5 depending on their perception of a player’s psychological performance during the SSG. Coaches were sometimes required to assess multiple players within a given match. They were instructed to leave a variable blank if they could not evaluate a player on a specific psychological trait. The criteria for scoring each of the psychological characteristics were as follows: 1 – poor, 2 – below average, 3 –

average, 4 – very good and 5 – excellent. The player’s scores for each variable were then accrued to provide an aggregate score out of 20 for each SSG. It is recognised that the psychological scoring chart has yet to be validated within an applied setting. It has been suggested that these measures likely possess a high level of ecological validity due to their reflection on current academy practices (Towlson et al, 2021b).

2.5 Statistical analysis

Data were analysed for normal distribution using Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests. To analyse the differences in technical performance between team size (4v4, 5v5, 6v6) and game format (maturity matched, mismatched, and mixed), a One-Way ANOVA was conducted. A Tukey post-hoc test was conducted if normal distribution was assumed and a Games-Howell post-hoc test was conducted if normal distribution wasn’t assumed.

Differences between maturity groups (More or Less) were assessed using an Independent samples T-Test or Mann-Whitney U analyses for those data that were parametric or non-parametric, respectively. Due to the categorical nature of the psychological scoring chart, non-parametric tests were conducted. A Kruskal-Wallis test was used to analyse the effect of team size and game format, and a Mann-Whitney U test was conducted for the impact of maturity. All analyses were completed using the software IBM SPSS statistics (version 26; SPSS, IBM, Chicago, IL, USA)

3. Results

Table 2. Technical and Psychological Descriptive Data for More and Less Mature Players

More Mature									
<i>Metric</i>	<i>Maturity Matched</i>			<i>Maturity Mismatched</i>			<i>Mixed Maturity</i>		
	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>
<i>Touches (n)</i>	25 ± 12	19 ± 5	19 ± 8	20 ± 8	19 ± 9	20 ± 7	22 ± 8	21 ± 6	17 ± 6
<i>Releases (n)</i>	10 ± 5	7 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 4	7 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 3	7 ± 2	6 ± 2
<i>Possession (n)</i>	10 ± 5	8 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 4	7 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 2	6 ± 2
<i>Time on the ball (sec)</i>	14.8 ± 9.4	12.2 ± 5.9	11.7 ± 7.4	12.3 ± 6.2	12.4 ± 8.9	12.4 ± 5.8	14.4 ± 8	14 ± 6.6	10.3 ± 6.2
<i>Psych Agg Score</i>	12 ± 3	9 ± 5	8 ± 4	14 ± 2	9 ± 4	8 ± 5	12 ± 5	11 ± 4	10 ± 5
Less Mature									
<i>Metric</i>	<i>Maturity Matched</i>			<i>Maturity Mismatched</i>			<i>Mixed Maturity</i>		
	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>	<i>4v4</i>	<i>5v5</i>	<i>6v6</i>
<i>Touches (n)</i>	23 ± 14	22 ± 8	16 ± 9	24 ± 15	20 ± 9	13 ± 8	22 ± 11	17 ± 7	15 ± 7
<i>Releases (n)</i>	8 ± 6	8 ± 3	5 ± 3	8 ± 6	7 ± 4	5 ± 3	7 ± 4	6 ± 3	5 ± 2
<i>Possession (n)</i>	8 ± 6	8 ± 3	6 ± 3	9 ± 6	8 ± 4	5 ± 3	8 ± 4	6 ± 3	5 ± 3
<i>Time on the Ball (sec)</i>	14.1 ± 11.6	12.8 ± 7.1	9.5 ± 6.1	15 ± 11.1	11.2 ± 8.5	7.6 ± 5.9	13.8 ± 8.8	10.7 ± 6.4	9.3 ± 6.4
<i>Psych Agg Score</i>	12 ± 6	12 ± 2	13 ± 4	11 ± 5	11 ± 4	12 ± 4	13 ± 4	10 ± 4	11 ± 5

3.1 Team Size and Technical Actions

During maturity-matched games, technical actions decreased as team size increased from 4v4 to 6v6 games for both more and less mature groups, except for releases which were lowest in 5v5 for more mature players. However, the analysis identified that team size had no significant effect on technical actions for both more mature (Touches: $p=0.088$; Releases: $p=0.12$; Possessions: $p=0.143$; Time on the Ball: 0.434) and less mature players (Touches: $p=0.054$; Releases: $p=0.051$; Possessions: $p=0.054$; Time on the Ball: $p=0.19$) during maturity matched games.

Similarly, no significant differences were present between 4v4, 5v5 or 6v6 maturity mismatched games for more mature players. However, it was found that team size had a significant effect on technical actions during maturity-mismatched games for less mature players (Touches: $p<0.001$; Releases: $p<0.001$; Possessions: $p<0.001$; Time on the Ball: $p=0.001$). Further analysis identified that during 4v4 games, less mature players had significantly more Touches (24 ± 15 vs 13 ± 8 , $p=0.002$ (3.29 - 16.84)), Releases (8 ± 6 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.006$ (0.92-6.05)), Possessions (9 ± 6 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.003$ (1.12-6.34)) and Time on the Ball (15 ± 11.1 vs 7.6 ± 5.9 , $p=0.004$ (2.16-12.56)) compared to 6v6 games. Less mature players had significantly more Touches (20 ± 9 vs 13 ± 8 , $p=0.003$ (1.96-10.82)), Releases (7 ± 4 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.001$ (0.96-4.41)) and Possessions (8 ± 4 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.001$ (1-4.53)) during 5v5 games than they did during 6v6 games. No significant differences were present between 4v4 and 5v5 games during maturity mismatched SSG.

During mixed maturity matches, it was found that team size significantly affected the technical actions displayed by more mature and less mature players. Further analysis identified that more mature players had significantly greater technical actions during 4v4 games compared to 6v6 games with regards to Touches (22 ± 8 vs 17 ± 6 , $p=0.001$ (1.9-8.64)), Releases (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.001$ (0.6-2.9)), Possessions (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.001$ (0.67-2.97)) and Time on the Ball (14.4 ± 8 vs 10.2 ± 6.2 , $p=0.008$ (0.94-7.43)). During 5v5 games, there were also significantly more Touches (21 ± 6 vs 17 ± 6 , $p=0.001$ (1.55-6.71)), Releases (7 ± 2 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.004$ (0.35-2.26)), Possessions (8 ± 2 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.007$ (0.28-2.17)) and Time on the Ball (14 ± 6.6 vs 10.3 ± 6.2 , $p=0.003$ (1.12-6.42)) compared to 6v6 games. During 4v4 games, less mature players took significantly more touches than during 5v5 games (22 ± 11 vs 17 ± 7 , $p=0.033$ (0.33-9.36)). Similar to more mature players, less mature players exhibited significantly greater technical actions during 4v4 games than they did during 6v6 games with regards to Touches (22 ± 11 vs 15 ± 7 , $p=0.001$ (2.82-11.62)), Releases (7 ± 4 vs 5 ± 2 , $p=0.007$ (0.5-3.71)), Possessions (8 ± 4 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.007$ (0.49-3.66)) and Time on the Ball (13.8 ± 8.8 vs 9.3 ± 6.4 , $p=0.009$ (0.98-8.01)). No significant differences were found between 5v5 and 6v6 for less mature players.

3.2. Team Size and Psychological Characteristics

During maturity-matched games, more mature players displayed significantly greater psychological characteristics during 4v4 games compared to 5v5 (12 ± 3 vs 9 ± 5 , $p=0.045$) and 6v6 (12 ± 3 vs 8 ± 4 , $p=0.02$) games. No significant difference was present between 5v5 and 6v6 for more mature players ($p=0.283$). In contrast to the more mature cohort, less mature players displayed similar psychological characteristics across 4v4, 5v5 and 6v6 games with no significant differences present ($p=0.098$).

Maturity-mismatched games produced a similar trend to maturity-matched games concerning the psychological characteristics displayed by more and less mature players. During 4v4 games, more mature players showed significantly greater psychological characteristics compared to 5v5 (14 ± 2 vs 9 ± 4 , $p < 0.001$) and 6v6 (14 ± 2 vs 8 ± 5 , $p < 0.001$) games. No significant difference was present between 5v5 and 6v6 games ($p = 0.569$). Less mature players displayed consistent psychological characteristics across 4v4, 5v5 and 6v6 games with no significant differences present as team size increased ($p = 0.498$).

Mixed maturity games elicited significantly greater psychological characteristics for more mature players during 4v4 compared to 5v5 (12 ± 5 vs 11 ± 4 , $p = 0.042$) and 6v6 (12 ± 5 vs 10 ± 5 , $p = 0.022$) games. No significant difference was present between 5v5 and 6v6 games ($p = 0.852$). In contrast to maturity matched and mismatched, less mature players displayed significantly greater psychological characteristics during 4v4 mixed maturity SSG compared to 5v5 (13 ± 4 vs 10 ± 4 , $p < 0.001$) and 6v6 (13 ± 4 vs 11 ± 5 , $p = 0.004$) mixed maturity SSG. There was no significant difference present between 5v5 and 6v6 mixed maturity SSG for less mature players ($p = 0.156$).

3.3. Game Format and Technical Actions

During 4v4 match-play, game format (maturity matched, maturity mismatched and mixed maturity) had no significant effect on the number of technical actions for both more mature (Touches: $p = 0.284$; Releases: $p = 0.129$; Possessions: $p = 0.214$; Time on the Ball: $p = 0.396$) and less mature players (Touches: $p = 0.855$; Releases: $p = 0.684$; Possessions: $p = 0.634$; Time on the Ball: $p = 0.872$).

Similarly, for 5v5 match-play, no significant effect was found between game format and the technical actions of more mature players (Touches: $p=0.484$; Releases: $p=0.808$; Possessions: $p=0.927$; Time on the Ball: $p=0.452$). Regarding less mature players during 5v5 games, despite the number of touches and time on the ball declining on average from maturity matched to maturity mismatched to mixed maturity, no significant differences were found between game formats (Touches: $p=0.73$; Time on the Ball: $p=0.538$). However, a significant effect was found for Releases and Possessions, with significantly more Releases (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 3 , $p=0.021$ (0.24-3.49)) and Possessions (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 3 , $p=0.018$ (0.31-3.72)) during maturity matched games compared with mixed maturity games for less mature players. No significant differences in the technical actions were observed when comparing maturity-matched to maturity-mismatched 5v5 SSG.

Game format had no significant effect on the technical actions of less mature players; however, significant differences were found for more mature players. Maturity-mismatched games elicited significantly greater Touches (20 ± 7 vs 17 ± 6 , $p=0.036$ (0.18-6.49)), Releases (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.002$ (0.65-3.27)) and Possessions (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.004$ (0.49-2.99)) than mixed maturity games for more mature players. Maturity-matched games elicited significantly more releases compared to mixed maturity games (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 2 , $p=0.043$ (0.04-3.29)) for more mature players.

3.4 Game Format and Psychological Characteristics

During 4v4 match-play, it was found that game format had no significance on the emergence of psychological characteristics of both more ($p=0.134$) and less (0.058) mature

players. A similar trend was also present during 5v5 match-play, with no significant differences between game formats for both maturity groups (More: $p=0.327$; Less: $p=0.382$). Regarding the less mature cohort, it was also found that game format had no significant effect on the display of psychological characteristics during 6v6 match-play ($p=0.104$). However, during 6v6 match-play, mixed maturity SSG promoted a greater display of psychological characteristics than maturity-matched SSG for more mature players (10 ± 5 and 8 ± 4 , $p=0.029$). Mixed maturity SSG also promoted significantly greater psychological characteristics than maturity mismatched (10 ± 5 vs 8 ± 5 , $p=0.002$) for more mature players. However, no significant difference was present between maturity-matched and maturity-mismatched games ($p=0.857$).

3.5 Maturity and Technical Actions

During maturity matched format, it was found that more mature players had significantly greater Releases (8 ± 3 vs 5 ± 3 , $p=0.018$) and Possessions (8 ± 3 vs 6 ± 3 , $p=0.025$) than less mature players during 6v6 match play. No other significant differences were present between more and less mature players during maturity-matched 4v4, 5v5 and 6v6 games. In 4v4 and 5v5 match-play during the maturity mismatched format, no significant differences were present between the technical characteristics of more and less mature players. More mature players had significantly more Touches (20 ± 7 vs 13 ± 8 , $p<0.001$), Releases (8 ± 3 vs 5 ± 3 , $p<0.001$), Possessions (8 ± 3 vs 5 ± 3 , $p<0.001$) and Time on the ball (12.4 ± 5.8 vs 7.6 ± 5.9 , $p<0.001$) during 6v6 maturity mismatched games than less mature players. During mixed maturity format, significant differences were present between more and less mature players during 5v5 match play, with more mature players having significantly more Touches (21 ± 6 vs 17 ± 7 , $p=0.005$), Releases (7 ± 2 vs 6 ± 3 , $p=0.001$),

Possessions (8 ± 2 vs 6 ± 3 , $p < 0.001$) and Time on the Ball (14 ± 6.6 vs 10.7 ± 6.4 , $p = 0.005$). More mature players also had significantly greater Possessions during 6v6 match play than less mature players (6 ± 2 vs 5 ± 3 , $p = 0.037$). No other significant differences were present between more and less mature players during mixed-maturity games

3.6. Maturity and Psychological Characteristics

Less mature players exhibited significantly greater psychological characteristics during 5v5 (12 ± 2 vs 9 ± 5 , $p = 0.019$) and 6v6 (13 ± 4 vs 8 ± 4 , $p < 0.001$) maturity-matched games compared to more mature players. More mature players displayed significantly greater psychological characteristics during maturity mismatched format during 4v4 (14 ± 2 vs 11 ± 5 , $p = 0.004$) compared to less mature players. Whilst not significant, less mature players displayed greater psychological characteristics (11 ± 4 vs 9 ± 4) on average during 5v5 mixed maturity games, and significantly greater psychological characteristics during 6v6 mixed maturity games (12 ± 4 vs 8 ± 5 , $p = 0.001$) compared to more mature players

4. Discussion

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of team size and game format on youth football players' technical exposure and psychological characteristics in youth football players during SSG. The main findings of the current study were threefold: 1) Smaller team sizes allowed less mature players greater technical exposure, particularly during maturity mismatched and mixed maturity SSG; 2) Smaller team sizes elicited a greater display of desirable psychological characteristics during bio-banded and mixed maturity SSG for more mature players; 3) Game Format appeared to have limited effect on the technical exposure and psychological characteristics of less mature players, irrespective of team size, and more mature players particularly during small team sizes.

For the present study, BB and mixed maturity games were completed using a round-robin style tournament, creating three game formats; Maturity Matched (More vs More, Less vs Less), Maturity Mismatched (More vs Less) and Mixed Maturity. During each of these game formats, the individual technical actions of less mature players were greatest during 4v4 match play. Technical actions decreased as team size increased, with significant decreases found in touches, releases, time on the ball and total possessions during maturity mismatched and mixed maturity SSG. It is natural to assume that with fewer players on the pitch, the respective technical actions of a player would be greater as fewer players can be in possession of the ball. This is consistent with previous research conducted by Clemente et al (2021) and Da Silva et al (2011) which found that during traditional SSG, smaller team sizes were associated with increased individual technical actions. Practitioners wishing to implement BB SSG to increase the technical exposure of less mature players must consider team size as an important game constraint. Findings from the current study indicate the

influence of BB on the technical exposure of less mature players is influenced by the number of players per team during BB SSG with smaller team sizes resulting in greater technical actions for less mature players when pitch size is controlled for. These findings suggest that smaller team sizes are more appropriate for manipulating the technical exposure of less mature players during BB SSG, irrespective of game format.

Maturity mismatched SSG is recognised as the most extreme game format for less mature players, exposing them to competition against physically superior opposition (Towlson et al, 2021b). Findings from the present study suggest that during maturity mismatched SSG, smaller team sizes elicit a significantly greater number of technical actions for less mature players, with significantly reduced technical actions during 6v6 compared to 4v4 and 5v5, respectively. The technical skills of less mature players may be masked due to the physical superiority of a more mature player inhibiting the emergence of such skills (Reeves et al, 2019). This notion is supported by the finding in the present study that during 6v6 maturity mismatched SSG, more mature players had significantly greater individual technical actions than less mature players. Previous research conducted by Towlson et al (2021b) suggested that exposing pre-PHV players to competition against post-PHV through maturity mismatched SSG allows pre-PHV players to display several desirable psychological characteristics. This present study found that the psychological attributes of less mature players remained consistent as team size increased during maturity mismatched SSG, suggesting that manipulating team size to promote the display of desirable psychological characteristics of less mature players during maturity mismatched SSG is ineffective. Despite the psychological characteristics of less mature players remaining consistent as team size increased, individual technical actions were greatest when smaller team sizes were utilised.

This suggests that practitioners should consider using smaller team sizes if less mature players are to be exposed to maturity mismatched SSG as it allows technical actions of less mature players to be maintained and exposes them to an environment that is suggested to promote the display of several desirable psychological characteristics (Towlson et al, 2021b).

In contrast to Towlson et al (2021b), the present study found that game format had no significant effect on the psychological characteristics of less mature players, with results remaining consistent across maturity matched, maturity mismatched and mixed maturity SSG. It is essential to acknowledge that Towlson et al (2021b) stated that less mature players' greater display of desirable psychological attributes during maturity mismatched SSG was particularly prominent when the Khamis-Roche (Khamis & Roche, 1994) method was used to estimate the maturity status of individuals. Therefore, a comparison between the studies must be made with caution as research has indicated that the Khamis-Roche (Khamis & Roche, 1994) method can better identify the onset of PHV compared to MO methods (Parr et al, 2020), as used in the present study. Therefore, findings must be interpreted with caution; however, game format may be limited in its ability to manipulate the psychological characteristics within less mature players, with results showing less mature players displayed consistent psychological characteristics across each game format. Despite the reduced physical challenge associated with maturity-matched competition, the consistent findings across game formats may indicate a habitual psychological response stemming from CA competition, where less mature players compete with and against physically superior, more mature players regularly. In senior football, players will compete against opposition of various anthropometric and physical fitness profiles, therefore, if this habitual response is present then less mature players would possess the necessary

psychological skills to cope with the demands of senior football, which is ultimately the aim of the academy process. Further research using a more robust protocol for estimating maturity status and a validated method for assessing the psychological characteristics of individuals should be conducted to confirm this notion.

During CA competition, more mature players typically rely on their physical superiority to dominate games and neglect their technical skillsets (Malina et al, 2015). A consequence of the physical dominance associated with advanced maturation is that more mature players aren't exposed to the challenge of competing against bigger and stronger opposition, which is thought to promote the development of superior psychological skills among less mature players (Cumming et al, 2018b). Maturity-matched BB may be a potential mechanism for exposing more mature players to the challenging environment required to develop such skill sets. Although not significant, the findings from the present study indicate smaller team sizes, on average, allow more mature players to display greater individual technical actions compared to larger team sizes. A similar trend was present concerning the psychological characteristics of more mature players during maturity-matched BB. During this format, 4v4 maturity-matched SSG elicited a significantly greater display of desirable psychological attributes than 5v5 and 6v6 maturity-matched SSG, respectively. Vygotsky's Zones of Proximal Development (ZPD) (Vygotsky, 1978) stipulates that children can only develop specific skills by engaging with older and more skilled children. Whilst it is acknowledged that Vygotsky's ZPD was not specific to a sporting context, it has been suggested that more mature players are more likely stretched within their respective ZPD due to competing with and against individuals of a similar physical profile during maturity-matched BB (Hill et al, 2020). Practitioners have acknowledged that a primary aim of academy football is to

develop players who are capable of competing within senior football (Relvas et al, 2010), therefore, a development programme that fails to expose players to appropriate learning environments to facilitate the development of the required skillsets is ultimately failing to prepare players for the demands of senior football. The findings from the current study indicate that if BB SSG aim to develop the technical or psychological skills of more mature players, then smaller team sizes would be optimal, with increased team sizes overstressing those individuals and potentially leading to reduced development of the skillsets required to cope with the demands of senior football.

During 4v4 and 5v5 SSG, it was found that game format had no significant effect on the technical exposure or psychological attributes displayed by more mature players. This may suggest that using BB to manipulate the technical and psychological skillsets of more mature players may be limited as similar results were present during mixed maturity SSG designed to reflect CA competition. This finding is in accordance with previous research (Towlson et al, 2021b; Towlson et al, 2021c), which identified that during 4v4 SSG, BB had limited effect in manipulating the technical actions and psychological traits compared to mixed maturity competition. Concerning the technical actions, Towlson et al (2021c) suggested that the small relative pitch (40-50m²) size used may have restricted the technical output of players; however, the present study used a fixed relative pitch size of 141m² and found similar findings. The relevance of the findings from the current study, coupled with the findings of Towlson et al (2021b) and Towlson et al (2021c) suggest that BB may be ineffective at manipulating the technical actions or psychological traits during 4v4 and 5v5 SSG. Therefore, 4v4 and 5v5 BB SSG may not be applicable to identify the technical and psychological skillsets of more mature players, which have been identified as desirable to talent selectors

(Sarmiento et al, 2018). Practitioners wishing to use BB to develop or identify the technical skillsets and psychological characteristics of more mature players should consider team size as an important game constraint. The present study indicates that the effectiveness of BB in manipulating technical and psychological measures within more mature players is influenced by team size and a greater number of players per team is necessary to influence the technical skillsets and psychological characteristics of more mature players.

Game format was found to affect both the technical actions and psychological characteristics of more mature players during 6v6 SSG. Results identified that more mature players had significantly greater touches, releases, and possessions during maturity mismatched SSG compared to mixed maturity SSG. During maturity mismatched competition, more mature players compete with physically inferior, less mature players. However, during mixed maturity SSG, more mature players may face opposition of a similar maturity status and physical profile. Previous research conducted by Abbot et al (2019) identified that early-maturing players had more successful tackles than late-maturing players during CA competition and suggested this was a result of the physical superiority of those early-maturing players. The physical superiority of more mature players during mismatched SSG may allow them to dominate duels; therefore, they can recover the ball from less mature players and protect it. This may result in an increased frequency of individual technical actions during maturity mismatched SSG compared to mixed maturity SSG where more mature players may face opposition of a similar physical profile, which may reduce the extent of their physical superiority. During maturity-matched SSG, more mature players have described an increased physical challenge due to competing with players of a similar maturity status (Cummings et al, 2017). Therefore, their ability to dominate duels

and recover possession or protect the ball will be reduced due to the increased physical equity associated with maturity-matched BB, possibly leading to fewer technical actions. The findings of the present study did not support this notion, with more mature players displaying a similar number of individual technical actions during 6v6 maturity-matched and mismatched SSG.

Research conducted by Towlson et al (2021a) discovered that during 4v4 SSG, post-PHV players become more central to passing networks and team dynamics during mixed maturity SSG compared to BB SSG. Less mature players often possess reduced anthropometric and physical fitness traits resulting in a sub-conscious reliance on more mature players (Towlson et al 2021a). The present study found no significant increase in individual technical actions during mixed maturity SSG compared to BB SSG across each team size. However, it was found that more mature players displayed significantly greater psychological characteristics during 6v6 mixed maturity SSG compared to both 6v6 maturity matched and mismatched SSG. Suppose the notion that more mature players become more integral to passing networks and team dynamics is applied to the current study. In that case, mixed maturity SSG may promote the display of desirable psychological attributes among more mature players. Late-maturing players have previously described maturity-matched BB as allowing them to adopt leadership positions and mentor younger players (Cummings et al 2017). With more mature players becoming more integral during mixed maturity SSG, perhaps this allows them the same opportunities described by late-maturing players during maturity-matched BB. Less mature players may subconsciously become reliant on the more mature players, which in turn could allow the more mature players to adopt positions of leadership and mentor the less mature players resulting in an increased display of desirable

psychological characteristics. During maturity-matched and mismatched SSG, the environment may not be conducive for more mature players to adopt such positions as they will be competing with and against players with similar anthropometric and physical fitness traits and therefore may be less integral to the team. This may explain the significant increase in psychological characteristics displayed by more mature players during 6v6 mixed maturity SSG compared to 6v6 maturity matched and mismatched SSG in the present study. These findings would then suggest that the use of mixed maturity SSG would allow more mature players a greater opportunity to develop and display several desirable psychological attributes compared to maturity-matched and mixed maturity SSG. This present study utilised mixed maturity as a control group designed to reflect the composition of CA-matched squads. With more mature players displaying greater psychological characteristics during 6v6 mixed maturity SSG compared to 6v6 BB SSG, it may suggest that CA-matched competition is an appropriate environment for more mature players to develop the required psychological skillsets necessary to compete in senior football, therefore, the use of BB SSG to develop such skillsets isn't required. This phenomenon wasn't present during 4v4 and 5v5 SSG; therefore, it must be interpreted cautiously and warrants further research. Towlson et al (2021a) suggested that practitioners wishing to develop the technical and tactical skills of early maturing players should consider the composition of teams (late: early maturing players) during mixed maturity SSG with early maturing players becoming more integral to passing networks and team dynamics. Future research should consider investigating this notion concerning the psychological characteristics displayed by more mature players during mixed maturity SSG, using robust maturity status assessments and a validated protocol for assessing the psychological characteristics of individuals.

5. Strength and Limitations

A strength of the present study is that a fixed relative pitch size (141m² per player) was used allowing a consistent approach to be implemented when increasing the number of players per team from 4v4 to 5v5 to 6v6. This allowed for the influence of increasing the number of players per team on technical and psychological measures during BB SSG to be examined in an isolated manner without other game constraints such as varying pitch sizes impacting upon results.

A limitation of the current study that must be acknowledged when interpreting the findings is that to estimate the maturity status of the participants, BB requires estimating the maturity status of individuals and then allocating them to a specific group (i.e., more or less; early or late) based on the findings. Therefore, it is critical to acknowledge any limitations associated with the selected method for estimating the maturity status of the cohort. Nevill and Burton (2017) suggested that the likelihood of invalid findings is increased because of chronological age being present on both sides of the prediction equation. Whilst this has been refuted by Fransen et al (2019), it is essential to consider. The use of predicted MO method, such as the Fransen method, has shown reduced levels of accuracy among individuals at either extreme of maturation, with findings suggesting an over- and under-estimation of age at PHV among early and late maturing individuals, specifically boys (Koziel & Malina, 2018). A strength of the present study is that measures were taken, in line with previous research conducted within a similar cohort (McMaster et al, 2021), to reduce the increased inaccuracy associated with individuals furthest away from the age at PHV. The present study implemented a cut-off level of ± 2.6 years from PHV which allowed for the recruitment of a sufficient number of participants to complete the study whilst attempting

to reduce the associated error for participants further away from PHV. Future research should consider using a more robust method for obtaining the maturity status of participants, such as the Khamis-Roche (Khamis & Roche, 1994) method, which has shown superior levels of accuracy when estimating age at PHV. Research conducted by Parr et al (2020) found that the Khamis-Roche (Khamis & Roche, 1994) method identified 96% of football players as undergoing PHV compared to the maturity offset method, which identified only 65%.

The present study collected data about the psychological characteristics of youth footballers during BB SSG using a psychological scoring chart which contained psychological components considered necessary by youth coaches and talent selectors when recruiting a player for TID programmes (Larkin and O'Connor 2017; Towlson et al. 2019). Despite the contents of the psychological scoring chart being viewed as essential by key stakeholders during TID programmes and its use within previous research conducted within a similar cohort to this present study (Towlson et al 2021b), the psychological scoring chart has yet to be validated and is said to contain psychological constructs lacking relevant psychometric grounding (Towlson et al 2021b). With the psychological scoring chart remaining unvalidated within the current body of research, findings about the psychological characteristics of participants must be interpreted with caution.

6. Practical Implications

The findings from the present study suggest two main practical applications for coaches and practitioners when designing SSG for BB to develop the technical and psychological skillsets of both more and less mature players. Firstly, smaller team sizes (i.e., 4v4) resulted in more individual technical actions for less mature players during maturity matched, mismatched, and mixed maturity SSG. Therefore, practitioners wishing to use maturity-matched BB to allow less mature players to express their technical skillsets for TID or technical development purposes should consider using smaller team sizes. Results of the current study evidenced that smaller team sizes, on average, increased the individual technical actions of less mature players during maturity-matched SSG. This finding is also important given that previous research has identified that maturity mismatched SSG may allow pre-PHV players to display several desirable psychological characteristics (Towilson et al, 2021b). If practitioners wish to expose less mature players to maturity mismatched SSG to assess their psychological skillsets, then the use of smaller team sizes would allow them to do so without reducing the number of individual technical actions. This could enable less mature players' technical and psychological skill sets to be identified or developed.

Secondly, a greater display of desirable psychological characteristics was present among more mature players when smaller team sizes were used in maturity-matched, mismatched, and mixed-maturity SSG. During CA competition, more mature players aren't exposed to the same developmental challenges as less mature players, which develop attributes such as problem-solving and resiliency (Towilson & Cumming, 2022). Therefore, they may be ill-prepared for the demands of senior football where they will face competition against players possessing similar anthropometric and physical fitness traits (Cumming et al, 2018a;

Malina et al, 2015), which would be a failure of the academy process. Results from the current study indicate that if practitioners wish to use maturity-matched BB to promote the development of desirable psychological characteristics of more mature players, then they should consider using smaller team sizes (i.e., 4v4).

7. Conclusion

The results from the current study suggest that during BB SSG, the use of smaller team sizes is favourable for developing the technical skillsets of both more and less mature players.

This finding is evidenced by the greatest number of individual technical actions for more and less mature players present during 4v4 SSG during maturity matched, mismatched, and mixed maturity SSG. Smaller team sizes also allowed more mature players to express more highly desirable psychological characteristics, with less mature players displaying consistent psychological attributes as team size increased. Findings also demonstrated that game format had a limited effect on the technical exposure and psychological characteristics of both more and less mature players, suggesting that BB may have limited ability to manipulate SSG's technical and psychological demands. Therefore, BB should not be considered as a replacement for CA competition but perhaps BB could be incorporated alongside CA competition within a development programme to provide players with a variety of learning stimuli to facilitate the holistic development of players (Abbot et al, 2019) whilst also providing TID practitioners with a different environment in which to view players.

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8. References

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Appendix 1

Table 1. Summary table of fixtures and game format per week

Details	N = 16	N = 20 (Week 1 players + 4 new players)	N = 24 (Week 2 players + 4 new players)
	Week 1 (4 Vs 4)	Week 2 (5 Vs 5)	Week 3 (6 Vs 6)
	Pitch Dimension: 40.3m x 28m	Pitch Dimension: 44.1m x 32m	Pitch Dimension: 47m x 36m
Bio-Banded	Less A Vs Less B	Less A Vs Less B	Less A Vs Less B
	More A Vs More B	More A Vs More B	More A Vs More B
	Less B Vs More A	Less B Vs More A	Less B Vs More A
	More A Vs Less A	More A Vs Less A	More A Vs Less A
	Less B Vs More B	Less B Vs More B	Less B Vs More B
	Less A Vs More B	Less A Vs More B	Less A Vs More B
6 matches per player, 30 minutes total playing time			
*** 5-minute wash out period ***			
Mixed Maturity	Mixed A Vs Mixed B	Mixed A Vs Mixed B	Mixed A Vs Mixed B
	Mixed C Vs Mixed D	Mixed A Vs Mixed B	Mixed A Vs Mixed B
	Mixed B Vs Mixed C	Mixed B Vs Mixed A	Mixed B Vs Mixed A
	Mixed D Vs Mixed A	Mixed B Vs Mixed A	Mixed B Vs Mixed A
	Mixed B Vs Mixed D	Mixed B Vs Mixed B	Mixed B Vs Mixed B
	Mixed A Vs Mixed D	Mixed A Vs Mixed C	Mixed A Vs Mixed C
6 matches per player, 30 minutes total playing time			

Appendix 2 – Psychological Scoring Chart

Psycho-Social Performance Criteria

Name of Player:

Bib (Number):

Academy Club and Age Group:

	Game 1 - Coach Initial:					Game 2 - Coach Initial:					Game 3 - Coach Initial:				
Criteria	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
<u>Positive Attitude</u> Positive reaction after a mistake, How they handle disappointments, Resilience; Ability to overcome adversities, Not wanting to give up.															
<u>Confidence</u> Brave, Wants to be involved, Wants the Ball, Wants the Ball under pressure, Wants to get into positions to receive the ball all the time, Have the guts to try and fail and do something different.															
<u>Competitive</u> Resolve, Desire, Hunger, Strong willed, Determination, Intense, Fighting approach towards wanting the Ball, Winning mentality.															
<u>X-Factor</u> Unpredictable, Creative, Thinks outside of the box															
<u>Game Score</u> (Won, draw or loss and write score)															